

PROVERBS AND SAYINGS IN LIFE

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Abstract: *Proverbs and sayings provide an excellent opportunity to get acquainted with the life and culture of the people for whom this language is native, they convince us that different peoples can have the same worldviews and moral values. The study of proverbs and sayings helps to understand the mentality and national character of the native speakers of this language. The correct and appropriate use of proverbs and sayings gives speech a unique originality and special expressiveness.*

Key words: *proverbs, sayings, speech, communication*

Proverbs and sayings are widespread genre of oral folklore, daily life and literature works . They have been accompanying people since ancient times. Such expressive means as precise rhyme, clear form, brevity, made proverbs and sayings persistent, memorable and necessary in speech. Proverbs should be discriminated from sayings. The main feature of the proverb is its completeness and didactic content. The proverb is differentiated by the incompleteness of the conclusion, the lack of an instructive character.

In live speech, a proverb can be reduced to a saying, just as a saying can develop into a proverb. Chinese proverbs (known in Chinese as 谚语, yànyǔ) are popular sayings taken from literature, history, and philosophers such as Confucius and Laozi. These short pearls of wisdom play an important role in daily communication in China, and are a great tool for expanding one's vocabulary and understanding of both Chinese culture and language.

For examples: “一言既出，驷马难追” (— A team of horses will struggle to chase down a spoken word.) was from "The Analects of Yan Yuan" (《论语·颜渊》), it means a word spoken can never be taken back, or a promise must be kept.

“三思而后行”(— Think thrice before you act.) was from "The Analects" (《论语》), it's like: "Look before you leap” .

As well as other literal works from ancient till nowadays e.g. 惩前毖后。 ('punish before prevent after')(— Punishing those who come before stops those who come after from doing something.)was from "Sacrificial Odes of Zhou" (《周

颂》) in the [Confucian classic](#) "Book of Songs" (《诗经》), it means: to criticize former mistakes firmly to prevent them happening again; or: learn from past mistakes to avoid future ones.

“无规矩不成方圆”(— Without standards, no boundaries are set.) was from the works of Mencius and his students (《孟子·离娄上》), it means: nothing can be accomplished without norms or standards; or: without rules, we're nothing but savages. “万事俱备，只欠东风”(— Everything's ready except the east wind.) was from the "Romance of the Three Kingdoms" (《三国演义》), this means that everything is ready except what is crucial. “人过留名，雁过留声”(— A person leaves a reputation, as a swallow leaves its call.) is from the 32nd chapter of Legend of Heroes (《儿女英雄传》), it means that someone's reputation is easily remembered. A proverb is a poetically designed aphorism, a saying is a speech, a turn of phrase, a common expression. “事实胜于雄辩。”(Facts beat eloquence.) was from Lu Xun's "Hot Wind" (鲁迅《热风题记》), it's like, "Actions speak louder than words."

M.A. Meshcheryakova, doctor of pedagogical sciences, interprets the proverb as “a finished, brief, figurative saying of a generalizing nature; instructive vital observation, which can be applied to the most diverse situations and cases; Small genre from of folklore”

Sometimes it is very demanding to distinguish a proverb from a saying or draw a clear line between these genres. A proverb borders on a proverb, and if one lexeme is added to it or the word order is changed, the proverb becomes a proverb.

In oral speech, saying often become proverbs, and proverb-sayings. Noteworthy are those expressive means by which the persistence or memorability of proverbs and sayings is achieved. Orally, sayings often become proverbs and proverbs into sayings. The expressive means with the help of which the resistance or memorization of sayings and proverbs is achieved deserve attention.

For example: *More haste, less speed*(欲速则不达)

Easy come, easy go (来去自由) (好借好还, 再借不难)

Like father, like son. (有其父必有其子)

Sayings are an accurate figurative expression that does not contain a generalized meaning. It is not a complete expression, but only part of it, possibly part of the proverb, an independent expression that gives speech expressiveness. It can also be a borrowing from a literary work.

Seeing is believing.(眼见为实)

Dead men tell no tales.(死人不会说谎)

Better late than never (晚做总比不做强)

Thus, there is no consensus on the definition of terms “proverbs” and “saying”. Each author interprets these definitions in his own way, but most linguists consider proverbs and sayings as stable phrase instructions, reflecting the features of the linguistic picture of the world of one or another people.

The sources of origin of sayings and proverbs in modern English are extremely diverse. Based on the theory of A.V. Kunin on the origin of proverbs, they can be divided into two classes: native proverbs and sayings and borrowed proverbs and sayings. *“Borrowed phraseological units, in turn, can be divided into intralingual and interlingual. Borrowings in foreign language from are allocated to a special group”*

Thus, four groups can be differentiated:

1. Native sayings and proverbs
2. Interlingual borrowings: borrowing from foreign languages by one or another type of translation;
3. Cross-cultural borrowings: borrowing from cross-cultural communication and languages merge (phraseological units borrowed from other variants are not numerous);
4. Sayings and proverbs borrowed in a foreign language form.

Conclusion

Proverbs and sayings are closely connected with the customs, cults and traditions of people, as well as with legends, various beliefs, historical events and realities. On the one hand, proverbs and sayings enrich people's lives, and on the other hand, people's lives are changed to make them richer and more vibrant.

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